

REFORMS IN EDUCATION AND TRAINING OF COMPETITIVE PERSONNEL - THE FOUNDATION OF THE COUNTRY'S DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

In this article, the reforms carried out in the higher education system during the years of independence, the development of the potential of young people in Uzbekistan, the creation of suitable conditions for their study and education, the annual increase of the admission quota for higher education, education Literally renewing the system, the scientific potential accumulated in Uzbekistan's educational institutions, its material and technical base, the quality indicators of personnel in the field of science and technology, imbalances in financial and material supply in the first years of independence, and the analysis of scientific research works are based on .

Key words: Education, science, development of society, higher education, development of individual and society, reform, education of young generation, social and economic development, "On Education" law, continuous education, mature specialist, scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel, scientific-research institutions.

INTRODUCTION

All the states that have historically existed in the territory of Uzbekistan have had their own educational system. Primitive forms of education are certainly manifested in the life processes carried out by older, experienced and capable family members in the family. Later, it changed to teacher-pupil, rir-murid and various other forms, and gradually began to look like collective educational institutions.

The effectiveness of any goals and reforms is achieved by science. No matter where it develops or appears, it will not fail to have its influence on world development. This can be seen from the fact

that science is the main factor in the rise of developed countries. The development of the society depends on the scope and logic of the implemented reforms. Only those reforms which are carried out with deep and comprehensive consideration, will make people's problems easier, their burdens lighter, their lives more comfortable, and find solutions to their problems. At the heart of the work being done, it is necessary to consider the long future along with the solution of today's problems.

Education is considered as the main, leading factor of social and economic development. The reason for such attention is that the most important value and main capital of modern society is a person who is able to search for new knowledge, acquire it and make non-standard decisions. Therefore, in the current period, education plays a decisive role in the development of individuals and society. Globalization and intense competition in the world economy are creating a need for continuous education throughout the life of a person, not lifelong education in the previous period.

From the first years of independence, attention was paid to the field of education, but it must be admitted that the reforms in the education system, without taking into account the development trends of the society, the demographic growth of the population, the aspirations of a significant group of young people, and the global technological processes in our country did not bring the expected results. During it, the problems increased and did not decrease.

The reforms being implemented under the leadership of the President of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev, of course, are carried out with a deep consideration of the demographic processes and urbanization, the thinking of humanity and the growing political outlook, consciousness and culture of our people, and the public interest. It has been almost 33 years since Uzbekistan gained state independence. Although thirty-three years is very short for history, it is a significant period for the development of society. During these years, a number of achievements have been achieved in the field of education in our country.

It is difficult to imagine the development of our country and society at the level of modern requirements without science. Today, in our country, attention is paid to science at the level of state policy, and the next seven years were full of great changes and updates in the field of education. The appearance of higher education institutions has changed radically, and the material and technical base has been strengthened. This, in turn, increased the desire for higher education among young people, increasing the quality and level of education.

It should be noted that the populist, fair and comprehensive reforms carried out under the leadership of our country's president for the past five years are showing their positive results in life. The people's interest has been put above all else, the principle that "the people should serve the people, not the state bodies, but the state bodies should serve the people" is gaining priority. Therefore, radical changes are being made in the activities of higher education institutions today. In recent years, it was very difficult to enter universities. There were few quotas, there were various problems in the entrance exams. Taking into account these issues in our country, the admission quota for higher education is increasing year by year. The education system is literally being renewed. The number of higher education institutions has increased from 77 in 2016 to 212 today. This, in turn, serves to train young people as knowledgeable, qualified specialists compatible with global development, and to help them find their place in life. According to the data of 2022, the level of inclusion of young people in higher education has increased by 38% or 4.2 times. 65 non-state higher education institutions were established. In addition, the number of foreign higher education institutions increased by 4.2 times.

Education is one of the main elements of human capital. In turn, the first 12 goals of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy are directly related to educational system reforms - further development

of pre-school, general secondary, professional and higher educational institutions and the improvement of the quality of education. Also, the Law "On Education" adopted in 2020 clearly defined the basic principles, educational system, types and forms of our country's education.

In addition to increasing the number of higher educational institutions and the number of students studying in them, the head of our state pays special attention to strengthening the material and technical base of higher educational institutions. New buildings are being built for higher educational institutions, their scientific laboratories are being equipped based on world educational standards. Ways of cooperation with foreign scientists are being developed in the course of education. Increasing the training of scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel in higher education institutions, increasing their scientific potential has become one of the main issues. That is, it is envisaged that each higher educational institution will connect and cooperate with industry, network research institutions, design bureaus, experience and innovation centers. As President Sh.Mirziyoyev noted, "...higher educational institutions should now focus on training mature specialists in their field, not just graduates." In other words, the head of our state showed that it is a necessity of life that the higher education system needs to be fundamentally changed in terms of quality.

In 2016-2018, more than seventy decrees, decisions and orders of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Cabinet of Ministers regarding the education sector were adopted. These very important legal documents became the basis for the process of qualitatively radical change and renewal of the education system in our country. Conclusions and suggestions, according to the conducted analysis, the main forms of organization of continuing education according to the international standard classification are divided as follows:

- formal education, including institutional educational organizations (schools, colleges, universities, etc.);

- non-formal education describes any educational activity not related to formal education. It should be noted that this form of education does not aim to certify students;

- informative (informal) education shows some innovative form of continuous education. An example of such a form can be independent education (at the individual level) or at work or in the family (at the group level).

In the current period, a new look and understanding of the role and importance of continuous education, which meets the needs of modern education, is required. Continuing education should meet social requirements, which are as follows:

- to combine the best traditions of the traditional education system with the world experience and scientific technologies of organizing new education; - flexibility and predictability;

- levels, types, content of science, educational needs of people and the state, integration of mixed fields;

- development of modern core competencies and skills;

- innovativeness.

Continuous education is one of the most important concepts of the innovative education model, which represents the basis of the development of every person throughout his life in the conditions of today's global economy. According to the analysis, in the practice of developed countries, it is significantly easier to implement the balance of approaches expected in additional education, because it is mainly studied by middle-aged people. Adult learners are somewhat successful people with a sufficiently high level of development. At each new stage of additional education, the goal of public

importance - the development of abilities and talents of every person for success in life at any age - can be achieved significantly faster.

Based on the above, the competitiveness of each country depends primarily on its level of education and science. The modern state of economic and social development puts more demands than ever on the quality of human activity and professional training. The requirements for assessing the level of suitability of a modern employee for a certain work activity are constantly changing and intensifying.

Darhaqiqat davlatimiz rahbari tomonidan olib borilayotgan oqilona siyosat, yoshlarga yaratilayotgan imkoniyatlar, fan va ta'lim ahlining jamiyatda tutgan mavqeyini oshirishga qaratilgan e'tiborlar Yangi O'zbekistonda varovon hayot barpo etishning asosiy omillardan biriga aylandi. Bu e'tibor yangicha fikrlaydigan, ma'suliyatli, tashabbuskor, raqobatbardosh, vatanparvar va fidoyi yosh avlodni kamolga yetkazishga xizmat qiladi. Yurtboshimiz ta'kidlaganlaridek: «Ma'naviy uyg'oq jamiyatni, o'z oldiga ulkan vazifalar qo'yib, kelajak sari ishonch bilan borayotgan xalqni hech kim o'z yo'lidan to'xtata olmaydi.

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